

INFLUENCE OF PHYSICAL PROPERTIES RANDOMNESS IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES STRENGTH

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ABSTRACT

Among the most important factors of applying the reliability concepts to the laminated composite materials are the deviations related with the physical characteristics at the layer level. Due to the large number of properties involved it is important the choice of the most relevant characteristics.

Using optimization techniques the optimal stacking sequence of the laminated and the respective failure load are determined. The optimal design space is generated through simulation along the loading field. When varying the materials physical properties the laminated composite strength field is determined and after manipulation of the relevant data, the randomness degree of the physical properties is obtained as function of the laminated composite strength. The level of importance of each physical property regarding the laminated stress failure is analysed and compared. This methodology allowed the generation of a set of random properties that most affect the structure reliability.

Keywords: reliability, physical properties, design space, simulation, randomness degree.

1. INTRODUCTION

The standard deviations of mechanical response of composite materials are relatively large and the strength of composite products depends on manufacturing processes and quality control. Indeed, the definition of structural design criteria is actually based on ultimate state theory rather than on service stress theory. Applying this methodology to composite materials, based on reliability concepts, has created new obstacles to researchers due to the complexity of the laminated composite materials.

For reliability analysis and design of composite structures the ply strength properties have been regarded as random variables by several researchers like as Yang [1], Wetherhold et al [2] and Fukunaga et al [3]. In general these physical properties do not have the same influence in the laminate strength deviations. On other hand another physical properties like ply elastic constants and ply dimensional characteristics show great influence in the laminate strength deviations. Due to the great number of random variables involved in the reliability analysis of laminate composite materials we propose in this work a methodology to choose the most relevant random variables.

2. RANDOM PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

In this analysis the random physical properties are well defined using a macromechanic point of view and it is assumed that the following properties of a unidirectional or fabric ply may be determined from relatively simple tests:

- i) Ply strength properties:
 - X - longitudinal tensile strength
 - X' - longitudinal compressive strength
 - Y - transverse tensile strength
 - Y' - transverse compressive strength
 - S - longitudinal shear strength
- ii) Ply elastic constants:
 - E₁ - longitudinal Young's modulus
 - E₂ - transverse modulus
 - E_s - shear modulus
 - c_p, ν - Poisson's ratio
- iii) Dimensional and anisotropic properties:
 - t_i - ply thickness
 - θ_i - ply angle

3. ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

The adopted methodology is a modified version of the Monte Carlo analysis, [4]. The fundamental step in a Monte Carlo analysis is the generation of one set of n random numbers with an appropriated probability distribution function (PDF) for each random parameter in the response equation. The response equation is then solved by using each random number in the set. Therefore, the response equation is solved n times. Finally, these values of response are analysed using statistical techniques.

Two important changes are introduced in the developed method:

- Although there is no information about the probability distribution function (PDF) for each physical property, it is not important in the present work context. The qualitative analysis for the system response is made only when there is some deviation of each physical properties. Then, for all random parameters, is taken a general standard deviation $\sigma = \Delta\pi_i$, $i=1, \dots, m$.

- The randomness of the laminated strength deviation, as a consequence of the deviation σ for the physical property π_i , is a function of the load field Φ . Thus, it is generated a set of pseudo-random numbers with equal probability, that regards the dependence from the load field.

Then, the developed method consists of the following steps:

1. Generation of a set of pseudo-random numbers with equal probability over the range 0 to 1 that represent the load field $\Phi = f(u_1, u_2, u_3)$.
2. The physical property π_i takes a general standard deviation $\sigma = \Delta\pi_i$.
3. Substitution in the mathematic model system of each pseudo-random number generated on the field Φ . The scalar field function $\Psi = F(\Phi, \Pi, \Theta)$ represents the laminated strength regarding the maximum efficiency, where Π is the physical property vector and Θ is the optimal angle stacking sequence vector corresponding to the maximum efficiency.
4. Generation of the scalar field $\Gamma = \Delta\Psi$ corresponding to the strength deviation of the field Φ . This scalar field coincides with the sample space of the system response.
5. Statistic analysis of the sample space $\Gamma = \Delta\Psi$ of the strength deviation.

3.1. Generation of the vectorial field Φ

The vectorial field Φ is a sample space derived from Ω through an application like as $g(u_1, u_2) = (u_1, u_2, u_3)$ with:

$$|u_1| + |u_2| + |u_3| = 1 \quad (1)$$

being the domain Ω defined by:

$$\Omega = \{ (u_1, u_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 : 0 \leq u_2 \leq 1 - u_1 \text{ and } u_1 \geq 0 \} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1 shows the relation among the vectorial field Φ and the domain Ω of the application g. It is a function that maps \mathbb{R}^2 into \mathbb{R}^3 .

Figure 1. Generation of the vectorial load field Φ through the application $g(u_1, u_2)$. Discretization of the domain Ω .

Since the values u_1 and u_2 have equal probability, it is correct to consider an equal discretization to both the respective domains. Then, it is considered of the following generation number law for u_1 and u_2 , where N represents the number of intervals of the discretization:

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \rightarrow i = 1 \rightarrow N \\
 \quad u_1 = \frac{i}{N} \\
 \rightarrow j = i \rightarrow N \\
 \quad u_2 = \frac{j}{N}
 \end{array} \quad (3)$$

Although development of the values for u_1 e u_2 is not completely random it maps uniformly all domain Ω and this means that the generated values have equal probability.

3.2. Mathematic model system

Since the composite laminated materials have a complex structure and behaviour it is very hard to adopt a mathematic model system that enables good generalization of this work. Indeed, there are several requirements related to the geometry and boundary conditions independency and development of the sample space data without great computational costs.

Thus, the mathematical model system includes the following features:

- elementary theory
- failure criterion
- material efficiency
- response parameters

Elementary theory

The present analysis is based on the Laminated Plate Theory where each ply or ply group is treated as a quasi-homogeneous material and is assumed linear strain across the thickness, [5], [6].

Using the Laminated Plate Theory one can define the following generalized stress-strain relation for the laminate:

$$\begin{bmatrix} [A] & [B] \\ [B] & [D] \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_6 \\ k_1 \\ k_2 \\ k_6 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_6 \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_6 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where:

- [A] = in-plane stiffness matrix
- [B] = coupling matrix between in-plane and flexure
= 0 when laminate is symmetric
- [D] = flexural stiffness matrix

Failure criterion

The laminate strength is based on the individual ply strength and it is evaluated using a failure criterion [6]. The failure criterion adopted is the quadratic interactive failure criteria of Tsai-Wu. This failure criterion is represented in strain space:

$$G_{ij} \epsilon_i \epsilon_j + G_i \epsilon_i = 1 \quad ; \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (5)$$

where G_{ij} and G_i are the strength parameters [2].

Considering a strength / stress ratio R or strength ratio, defined by Tsai in reference [6], and regarding the failure criterion in strain space :

$$a R^2 + b R - 1 = 0 \quad (6)$$

where $\{\epsilon\}_{\max,ult,allow} = R \{\epsilon\}^{app}$, $a = G_{ij} \epsilon_i^{app} \epsilon_j^{app}$ and $b = G_i \epsilon_i^{app}$.

The failure criterion is applied to each ply within the laminate and the ply with the lowest R will fail first, thus, *First Ply Failure* (FPF). For a laminate with n plies its strength is associated to the value

$$R_{\min} = \text{MIN} (R_k, k = 1, \dots, n) \quad (7)$$

which is a measure of laminate efficiency.

Material efficiency / Formulation of the optimization problem

Since the thicknesses and ply number are fixed the material efficiency of laminated composites depends only on the plies orientations. In the proposed method the study of the strength deviations relates to the maximum laminate efficiency for all points of the domain Ω . Using this uniform condition the optimal design space is generated through the simulation along the loading field.

The laminate efficiency objective function is

$$W(\theta) = R_{\min} \quad (8)$$

and the design variables are the angle plies θ_i , $(i = 1, \dots, n)$.

The mathematic problem definition is

$$\text{Maximize } W(\theta) \quad (9)$$

The optimal solution was performed by a *branch and bound* technique regarding several heuristic features [7].

The optimal solution for each point on the load field Φ is mapped from Ω and represented by the angle vector Θ . The optimal value $W(\theta)$, corresponding to the optimal solution, is \bar{R}_i and these values form the scalar field $\Psi = F(\Phi, \pi, \Theta)$.

Response parameters

The load failure $\{ P_c^i \}$ for each point i of the scalar field Ψ , can be obtained through Equation 10. The scale factor q_{ref} is a function of the laminate thickness and is selected at the begin. This scale factor is related with the physical interpretation of all values of the space design $\Psi = F(\Phi, \pi, \Theta)$.

$$\{ P_c^i \} = \bar{R}_i q_{ref} \begin{Bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

When one considers a deviation $\sigma = \Delta\pi_i$ for each physical property there is a correspondent deviation $\Delta\bar{R}_i$ in the optimal strength ratio \bar{R}_i . The deviation in the load failure ΔP_c^i is equal to $\Delta\bar{R}_i$.

Thus, the laminate strength deviations is represented by the scalar field $\Gamma = \Delta\Psi$, i.e., the deviations in the space design Ψ . Finally, Γ is the sample space which is analysed statistically.

The implemented methodology in the statistical analysis has as scope to show the fundamental features of the randomness behaviour of the laminated composite when subjected to some deviation in the physical properties. This features are the following:

- the range and signal effects in the laminate strength
- the relation between the system response and the deviation in the physical properties
- the gradient of the deviation strength (or load failure) on load field and its critical points
- the importance and correlation between the several system responses

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

A symmetric angle-ply (plus 0° and 90°) laminate was considered with eight plies of glass E/epoxy composite designed by Scotch-ply 1002 [6]. The laminate is subjected to in-plane loads N_1, N_2 and N_6 or moments M_1, M_2 and M_6 . The two kinds of loads are studied independently and two sample spaces $\Gamma = \Delta\Psi$ are obtained for the strength deviations. The statistical analysis of the two sample spaces is performed independently rather than using superposition adding effects.

The standard deviations $\sigma = \Delta\pi_i$ regarding the mean values of the ply physical properties is $\pm 10\%$ and -5% , with the scope to study the range and the signal effects.

The load failure deviations ΔP_c^i are represented in percentual values. Figure 2 plots the graph of the scalar field $\Gamma = \Delta\Psi$ on the domain Ω . It is useful a qualitative analysis of the laminate strength deviations because in sample space it is possible to define the relation between the load components, the deviations and location on Ω .

Figure 2 shows that the laminate strength deviations are very dependent of the load components. The simmetry presented is related to simulation load field through the space design and it was verified to the angle-ply laminates that are orthotropic composites.

For this numerical example, the results show that the signal of the deviation response may be different of the signal of the ply physical property deviations. This is more remarkable in the ply elastic constants. On other hand the results obtained regarding deviations σ with other magnitude and signal have shown a linear influence in the field Γ when compared with the respective values for $\sigma = -10\%$.

Figure 2. Plots of the sample space Γ of strength deviations on domain Ω , for a standard deviation $\sigma = -10\%$ in transverse tensile strenght, Y. In-plane loads $N_1, N_2 \in N_6$.

Several statistical parameters like as means, standard deviations, variances,etc. were calculated. For simplicity we adopted in this work a graphical representation based on frequency histograms, plots of percentiles and confidence intervals. There are many parameters in this analysis and so, we represent only the most importants.

Figure 3 shows the frequency histograms of load failure deviation ΔP_c^i for a standard deviation $\sigma=-10\%$ in each of the following physical properties: transverse tensile strength, Y , longitudinal shear strength, S , longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1 and transverse modulus, E_2 . The laminates were subjected to in-plane loads $N_1, N_2 \in N_6$.

The confidence intervals of the failure load deviations ΔP_c^i are presented in Figure 4. It is possible to compare the influence of the ply physical properties deviations in laminate strength when subjected to flexural loads $M_1, M_2 \in M_6$.

Figure 3. Frequency histogram of the failure load deviations ΔP_c^i (%) for a standard deviation $\sigma=-10\%$ in physical properties of the ply of the laminate. In-plane loads N_1, N_2 and N_6 .

Figure 4. Confidence intervals of the failure load deviations ΔP_c^i (%), for a standard deviation $\sigma=10\%$ in physical properties of the ply of the laminate and t distribution. Flexural loads M_1 , M_2 and M_6 .

Table 1 presents a summary of general information obtained in statistical analysis of the sample space for all ply strength properties and ply elastic constants. The values in shaded form are regarded the most important and they are related with the laminate behaviour. A further analysis will be able to conclude about the influence of the physical properties randomness in laminate strength.

		FLEXURAL LOADS				IN-PLANE LOADS			
		$ \Delta P_c \leq x \%$				$ \Delta P_c \leq x \%$			
π_i	x	2,5	5,0	7,5	10,0	2,5	5,0	7,5	10,0
	X'		85	95	97	99	80	100	-
X		92	98	99	100	88	92	95	98
Y'		100	-	-	-	100	-	-	-
Y		30	42	55	70	8	12	30	75
S		45	55	65	100	68	88	95	99
v		100	-	-	-	100	-	-	-
E		92	100	-	-	58	80	96	100
E1		68	70	100	-	10	15	27	97
E2		64	70	90	100	12	26	56	100
		OBSERVATIONS (%)							

Table 1. Classification of the laminate load failure deviations (in modulus) for a standard deviation $\sigma=10\%$ in the ply physical properties.

An interesting behaviour is that the optimal solution Θ in each point of the domain Ω do not change when it is introduced a deviation $\sigma=10\%$ in the ply physical properties and it means that laminate strength deviations are little sensitive to deviations in angle ply physical property.

On other hand the results shown that the failure load deviations ΔP_c^i on domain Ω are

uniformly distributed for in-plane loads or flexural loads. when regarding a deviation $\sigma=10\%$ in ply thickness. The failure load deviation is equal to the ply thickness deviation when the laminate is subjected to in-plane loads but it is approximately twice when subjected to flexural loads and to both cases the signal response is the same of the ply thickness deviation.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the reliability analysis of the laminated composite materials there are a great number of random variables as for example its ply physical properties wich means a complex problem of analysis.

Using a modified version of the Monte Carlo analysis a new methodology was proposed being the scope to study the influence of the physical properties randomness in laminated composite strength and further more, the choice of the most relevant characteristics.

A numerical problem was presented applying this methodology to the angle-ply laminates. Thus, with the results of the Table 1 we are able to rank the physical properties in respect to its influence in laminate strenght and this is presented in Table 2.

ΔP_c	LOADS	
	FLEXURAL	IN-PLANE
Small magnitude on all domain	Y', v, E_s	X', Y', v
Small magnitude in general, but high critical point values	X, X'	X, S, E_s
Great magnitude, on a large range of the domain	Y, S, E_1, E_2	Y, E_1, E_2
	Π_i	

Table 2.

Indeed, for the angle-ply laminates the most relevant physical properties are the transverse strength, Y , the shear strength, S , the longitudinal Young's modulus, E_1 and the transverse modulus E_2 . On other hand, the results show that the ply thickness is also a property that affects in very important manner the laminate strength deviation.

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